

Diphenylamine-Ferricyanide Couple as a pH Responsive System

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EARLIER redox indicators like ferroin, nitroferroin together with redox couples [Ce(III)-Ce(IV)] have been employed as acid-base indicators¹. The use of diphenylamine type of compounds along with ferricyanide-ferrocyanide couple as pH indicators in the acid-base titrimetry for the estimation of acetic acid, benzoic acid, succinic acid, tartaric acid, oxalic acid, sulphuric acid and hydrochloric acid with sodium hydroxide is reported here.

Titration Procedure :

Aliquots of different acids (0.1 *N*) mentioned above are taken in an Erlenmeyer flask followed by 1.0 ml of the amine solution (sodium diphenylamine sulphionate in water and other amines in methanol) (0.01 *M*) and 1.0 ml of potassium ferricyanide (0.1 *M*). The mixture is titrated with a standard solution of sodium hydroxide (0.1 *N*) till the colour is changed from pale green to orange.

Results and Discussion

Both direct and indirect titrations can be carried out successfully. Weak bases cannot be titrated satisfactorily. However, carbonate is titratable to the first dissociation stage only. The relative percentage error and the standard deviation are shown in Table 1. The pK_{In} value obtained was 9.9. The pK_{In} value and other experimental observations were carried out using sodium diphenylamine sulphionate.

TABLE-1.

Acid	Relative Percentage error	Standard deviation
Sulphuric Acid	±0.33	0.024
Hydrochloric Acid	±0.33	0.023
Acetic Acid	±0.28	0.013
Benzoic Acid	±0.23	0.060
Oxalic Acid	±0.31	0.023
Succinic Acid	±0.28	0.060
Tartaric Acid	±0.23	0.028

The indicator action is due likely to the formation of non-protonated orange coloured oxidative form of diphenyl benzidine produced on oxidation of diphenylamine with ferricyanide in alkaline medium (>8.5 pH) and its conversion to the protonated green form in acid medium (<8.5 pH) and vice versa.

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Reference

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Studies with Chromium Ferrocyanide Epoxy Resin Based Ion-exchange Membranes

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INORGANIC ion exchangers have been sparsely used in the preparation of solid ion selective membrane electrodes^{1,2}. The reason for limited use of these materials in the development of ion selective electrodes is that, in general, they undergo ion exchange with large number of ions and obviously electrodes based on such materials are not expected to be specific to a particular ion. However, these membrane electrodes, inspite of being not very specific to a particular ion, can be used for the estimation of ions by potentiometric titrations using the membrane as indicator electrode³⁻⁶. In a recent communication⁷ we have reported on the use of chromium ferrocyanide membrane electrode in the potentiometric titrations of some bivalent metal ions with ferrocyanide ion. This membrane electrode though not very specific to ferrocyanide ion showed linear response to this ion in 10^{-1} - 10^{-6} *M* concentration range.

Ferrocyanide ion forms stable complexes with transition metal ions and is used in quantitative analysis⁸, extraction⁹ and co-precipitation¹⁰. So in view of analytical importance of metal ferrocyanides, further titrations of some trivalent metal ions have been carried out using chromium ferrocyanide membrane as indicator electrode and results of these studies are reported in this communication.

Experimental

Potassium ferrocyanide (B.D.H. AnalaR) was used as such. All other chemicals were of analytical grade. Dilute solution of ferrocyanide was prepared by diluting 0.1 *M* stock solution of potassium ferrocyanide, fresh every day.